

A NOVEL CHARACTERIZATION OF THE MECHANICAL PROPERTIES OF PAPER-BASED MATERIALS

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Abstract: This study presents a novel approach to characterizing the mechanical behavior of paper-based materials with a focus on their cushioning performance. By analyzing cushioning curves obtained through controlled compression tests, the energy absorption capacity and deformation characteristics of various paper structures were evaluated. The results demonstrate how material composition, layering, and structural design influence the cushioning response. These findings offer valuable insights for optimizing paper-based packaging solutions as sustainable alternatives to traditional foams and plastics.

Keywords: cushioning, paper, packaging, drop test

1 INTRODUCTION

Commercial goods are commonly encased in packaging buffers to protect them from damage due to vibration and impact shock during handling and transportation (G. Kun). The materials used to fabricate protective packaging are usually plastic foam such as EPS with good cushioning performance and cost-effective but not friendly to the environment (L. Andena). The growing trend towards the use of environmentally friendly packaging has led to an increase in the research and use of alternative biobased packaging solutions. Considering this paper-based packaging (molded pulp, honeycomb paper, etc.) already offers established sustainable packaging solutions that is recyclable, biodegradable and compliant with ISO 14000 and European Green Dot standards (S. W. Lye). Usually, the paper packaging solution are implemented for protection of lightweight structures such as small domestic appliances, electronic components, food products, etc.

Figure 1: Sustainable design of protective packaging using experimental-numerical approach

Although the paper-packaging materials and corresponding numerical design methods are already well established, they cannot be readily used to design packaging of heavy and complex home appliances for several reasons (G. Kun,). Firstly, these materials exhibit high stiffness before plastic deformation which makes them far from being regarded as an ideal cushioning material. Moreover, the established paper packaging solutions have comparable cushioning performance to EPS only at low static loads and low drop heights (G. Kun). Therefore, to improve the cushioning performance, the design of the paper packaging rely on the numerical structural optimization to reduce vibration transmissibility and to increase shock absorption in the case of single and multiple impacts (T. Fadji).

2 EXPERIMENTAL INVESTIGATION OF HONEYCOMB-PAPER CUSHIONING PROPERTIES.

Cushioning of packaging materials is typically evaluated in terms of the maximum deceleration versus the static stress for a specific drop height and cushion thickness. This enables one to obtain cushioning curve that defines minimum cushioning area to obtain best shock absorption. These standard methods provide a general guidance to the evaluation of cushioning performance. Here the standard impact-based test facility is proposed as shown in Fig. 2.

Figure 2: Experimental determination of honeycomb cushioning characteristics; a) Experimental test rig, b) Specimen before and after testing.

In Fig. 3 the cushioning curves obtained by measuring honeycomb panels with 20mm thickness are presented. The curves were obtained by performing the measurement with test samples of different cross-sections and considering multiple successive impacts. It can be observed that the cushioning curves change significantly in the event of consecutive impacts. The reason for this is that the honeycomb structure is deformed and as a result loses its cushioning ability, especially at high static contact pressures.

Figure 3: Measured cushioning curves for honeycomb panel of height 20mm at multiple subsequent impacts.

The optimal static pressure for analyzed honeycomb panels (thickness 20mm) is between 10kPa and 15kPa.

3 PAPER-BASED PACKAGING DESIGN METHODOLOGY

The paper-based packaging design methodology is demonstrated on the packaging design of the tumble dryer as shown in Fig. 4a. The entire packaging concept is based on folding through V-groove cuts without gluing. The principle of packaging folding can be clearly demonstrated by the unfolded and folded configuration of packaging corner (Fig. 4b).

Figure 4: Design concept of the paper honeycomb packaging for Gorenje tumble dryer; a) The packaging together with appliance, b) Folding concept.

To enhance the packaging protective performance, a static analysis was firstly carried out to deduce the contact pressures due to the weight of the appliance (Fig. 5a). The calculated stresses on the bottom part of packaging are presented in Fig. 5b. The contact areas are deduced in such a way that they are close to the optimal pressure of 15kPa to achieve the best cushioning performance. The static pressure analysis is carried out for both for the vertical impact and the impact from the side of the appliance.

Figure 5: Calculation of static loads on the packaging; a) Application of gravitational load, b) Calculated static pressures on the bottom part of the packaging.

With an optimized packaging design, the simulation of loads caused by impacts during transport is then carried out. These loads are usually determined based on the acceleration measurements during standard transportations tests. This includes the drop test and the side impact test, also known as the slope test. In Fig. 6 the loads applied to the sidewall during the slope test are presented along with induced stresses on the appliance. These simulations make it possible to identify stresses that could potentially lead to plastic deformation and breakage of an appliance.

Figure 6: The simulation of impact on the sidewall during slope test; a) Application of acceleration loads, b) Stresses on the appliance during impact.

Based on the numerical simulations, the final concept of the packaging design is deduced and the prototypes of the packaging are produced as shown in Fig. 7. With the prototype packaging, it is then possible to conduct an actual transportation test and in that way finally validate the proposed concept of packaging design.

4 CONCLUSIONS

The proposed approach for paper packaging design is based on an interdisciplinary research that integrates the state-of-the-art dynamics simulation methods with the latest advances in paper material technology. It is demonstrated that suitable geometric design of honeycomb packaging makes it possible to improve the paper packaging cushioning characteristics even at multiple transportation shock loads. The presented design methodology enables development of a sustainable and recyclable packaging solutions even for heavy home appliances. This will allow GORENJE to expand its sales on markets that have already taken significant regulations towards sustainability and recyclability.

Figure 7: The actual prototype of paper honeycomb packaging; a) Packaged appliance in cardboard box, b) Inner view of packaging design.

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